

Analysis of Fires, Prevention and Regulations in UK buses from 1994 to 2013

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Abstract

This paper quantifies the impact of fire prevention regulations on the safety of UK buses from 1994 to 2013 in a way not done before. The fire safety of passenger transport in buses has received little attention in the technical literature. However, fire statistics show that buses are significantly riskier than other modes of transport like cars, shipping, rolling stock or aviation. This is in great part due to the lower fire safety regulatory requirements for buses, which are less stringent than other modes of transport. The statistical data used in this paper were collected by the UK government and show that the number of bus fires has increased fivefold, up to 761 bus fires per year in 2013, in the last five decades. Further analysis shows that this big increase is driven mostly by the ever-growing fleet of buses. We show that the number of bus fires would have been even greater if new fire safety regulations had not come into place in 1995 and 2001. These European regulations affecting the UK increased the safety requirements in buses, especially focused on prevention via flammability. The cross analysis of the arrival of new regulations with statistical data on bus fires, combined with a simple linear model based on fleet size shows that prevention has reduced the probability of a fire in the UK by about 1.6 times. This is the first time that the impact of fire prevention is quantified in buses, making a case for their importance and effectiveness. The approach developed here could also be of help to analyse the effect of regulations on other data fire sets, modes of transport or safety systems.

1. Introduction

We continue learning of the sad news all over the world of fatalities and injuries caused when a bus catches fire, immediately after a collision or in other circumstances. Buses, which typically carry dozens of passengers, have the potential for a greater number of deaths and injuries and greater property losses than smaller vehicles. In fact, buses are amongst the riskiest forms of transport regarding fire hazards. According to the statistical data in the UK ([1] [2]) the frequency of bus fires per vehicle is 2.3 times higher than in a car, similar to heavy goods vehicles, 8 times higher than trains, and 2.7 times higher than ships [3]. This is in great part due to the lower fire safety requirements in buses, which are less stringent than for other modes of transport. For example, actual fire prevention requirements in buses [4-6] do not cover aspects such as the limitation of peak heat release rate, the smoke yield or the toxicity, unlike trains, planes, and ships [7].

Fire engineering shows that the safety of a system is made of a series of layers of protection which act as barriers [8-10] (prevention, detection, evacuation, compartmentation, suppression, and structural resistance). While all these layers have a role, they are not equally important, either in terms of benefits or costs. This paper presents a systemic approach to analyse the impact of the prevention layer to the specific system of buses in the UK. By buses, we mean multiple-passenger road vehicles. We examine the gradual improvement of fire regulations in buses and quantify their effects in terms of reduction of fires. The proposed methodology is based on the difference-in-difference analysis of the standards of fire protection and the statistics of bus fires in the UK [11, 12]. This analysis reveals how the improvement of the prevention layer has reduced the number of fires over years.

This paper is divided in four parts: first part identifies the fire scenarios to be found in buses, the second part defines the layers of fire protection in buses, with emphasis in the prevention layer. The third section presents the key UK/European regulations in bus safety. The last part studies the UK data and applies the proposed methodology for quantifying the impact of the fire prevention layer in buses.

2. Typical Fire Scenarios

Fire statistics in the UK, Sweden and USA all highlight three typical fire scenarios of more importance for buses [13, 14]. These scenarios are based on the ignition location of the fire): fire within the passenger compartment, fire within the engine compartment and fire within the wheel well compartment. See Figure 1. Table 1 shows that across these four countries, most bus fires start in the engine compartment, follow by fires in the wheel well, and the passenger compartment.

Figure 1. The location of the most typical fire scenarios for buses based on the fire statistics in the UK, Sweden, Norway and USA.

Table 1. Percentage of fires by typical fire scenarios. The percentages provided by BRE and SP are based on the probability of bus fires during the analysed period. The percentage provided by NFPA are based on the frequency of bus fires during the analysed period.

Location ^a	UK (BRE, 1964- 1969)	Sweden & Norway (SP, 1996-2004)	Sweden (SP, 2005- 2013)	USA (NFPA, 1980- 2003)
P	15%	4%	4%	12%
E	58%	71%	63%	69% ^b
W	14%	24%	21%	
Others	13%	1%	16%	19%

^a Location: P-passenger compartment, E-engine compartment and W-Wheel well compartment. See Figure 1.

^b Fire data in USA does not differentiate between fire within the engine compartment or wheel compartment.

The passenger compartment is where the occupants are situated, the passengers, drivers and crew [6]. Modern buses use materials that are flammable, such as synthetic foams, plastics, cotton, wool and cellulose for the seats, supports, curtains and blinds, to provide an appropriate comfort level. The main ignition sources [13, 14] within the passenger compartment are electrical failure, intentional actions (arson) and accidental ignition by any passenger (i.e., cigarette or lighter).

The engine compartment is a separate space where multiple flammable materials can be found, such as fuel (gasoline or

diesel), engine oil, transmission oil, plastic parts and rubber seals. The main sources of ignition [14] are electrical failures.

The wheel compartment is the open space where the wheels, transmission system and brakes are installed. It contains flammable materials such as rubber of the tyre, plastic parts, brake fluid and lubricants for the bearings [16]. Excessive friction because of overbraking, frozen bearings, underinflated tyres, or lack of lubrication are causes of overheating and ignition.

3. Layers of Fire Protection in UK Buses

Fire protection engineering shows that safety is achieved by creating a series of layers, which act as fire barriers. The following descriptions are based on buses. The next section identifies the links between the European regulations and the layers of fire protection.

The Prevention Layer aims at avoiding a fire or to greatly reduce its initial size. This is based upon the disruption of the fire triangle - oxygen, heat, and fuel. Eliminating oxygen is not viable in buses, so prevention is focused on removing fuel and ignition (heat). The prevention layer is divided into three sublayers: flammability, fuel control and ignition. Prevention via reduced flammability is based on choosing materials of low flammability which is typically required via flammability tests for the passenger compartment, and more recently for the engine compartment too [17]. In the wheel compartment, flammability tests are not required to date. Prevention via fuel control: For the passenger compartment, fuel control is based on eliminating or reducing the amount of fuel present in the bus. Note that movable fuel load in luggage and personal passenger items is most difficult to control. For the engine and wheel compartments, it is necessary to avoid fuel leakages and impose appropriate levels of maintenance [18]. Prevention via eliminating of ignition sources like electrical failure and hot surfaces requires an appropriate maintenance level [18].

The Detection Layer aims at quickly identifying and giving alarm about flames or smoke as soon as possible. Quick

detection enables the effectivity of the other layers, for example favouring quicker reaction times, more time for evacuation and earlier suppression. In passenger compartments, visual detection is important, and the driver or passengers can play a key role for monitoring arson or accidents. From 2014, the European Regulation [19] requires automatic alarm systems for smoke or excess installed in the toilet, driver area and baggage compartment. The engine compartment is required to be equipped with an alarm system [19] including acoustic and visual signals to the driver. No regulations have been established yet regarding detection in the wheel well.

The Evacuation Layer aims at moving people away from harm's way and out of the bus before the conditions become untenable. In order to achieve a short evacuation time, passenger compartments need at least two exit doors [18], emergency escape windows, and imposed a maximum number of passengers allowed. Important factors are an appropriate evacuation procedure and training of drivers and crew. Safety announcements and flyers inform passengers about the evacuation procedures.

The Compartmentation Layer aims at avoiding fire spread and smoke movement between compartments. The engine compartment can be fire-proof and separated from the passenger and wheel compartments using fire resistant materials. Current regulations do not require compartmentation of the wheel compartments despite studies [17] showing that fire in the wheel well can spread into the passenger compartment.

The Suppression Layer aims at extinguishing the fire at the earliest stages to avoid growth [18, 20]. Regulations [19] establish that buses must be equipped with fire extinguishers, and that at least one should be located near the driver, and properly training. To date, no regulation has established the mandatory use of automatic suppression systems in buses despite studies [20, 24] showing the advantages of using them. For example, Swedish insurance companies require suppression systems in the engine compartment since 2004. The arrival of the Fire Brigade and use of water hoses is part of this layer as well.

4. Regulation for Fire Protection in UK Buses

In the European Union, the fire protection in buses was first standardized in 1995 by the European Directive 95/28/EC regulating the burning behaviour of materials used in the interior of motor vehicles [4] (it was adapted to Regulation No. 118 [5] in 2005). This first directive was followed by Regulation No. 107 [19] in 2001. Note that regulations are addressed to all members' states and are applied in full. They are directly applicable without the need for national legislation. On the top of that, Directives are also addressed to all member states but they require an objective to be achieved by a given date. National authorities must draw up legislation in order to comply with the directive within a certain time frame.

Directive 95/28/EC requires three types of flammability tests for interior materials in the passenger compartment: horizontal burning rate of materials, melting behaviour of materials and vertical burning rate of materials. This Directive is applied for vehicles carrying more than 22 passengers and is not applicable for standing passengers or urban use (city buses). It should be noted that city buses are out of the scope of this paper. This regulation is largely based on the requirements for buses in the USA [25] brought into force as Federal Motor Vehicle Safety Standard (FMVSS) 302 in 1972.

The UNECE Regulation No.107 improved the fire protection of buses in Europe with a first version on the Regulation published in 2001 (Different updates have been released until its last version in 2014 [19]). Regulation No. 107 covers different topics related to fire prevention. The materials in the engine compartment should not contain flammable soundproofing and not liable to become impregnated with liquid fuel, lubricant or another combustible material. Also, a partition shall be fitted between the engine compartment and any other source of heat. On the top of that, other specifications are required related to the insulation and protection of electric equipment, the need for non-combustible material near any source of heat.

Directive 95/28/EC became the UNECE Regulation No.118 in 2005 [5] which has had different updates since then, such as in 2010 with the addition of a new test to determinate the

capability of materials to repel liquid fuels or lubricants, which allow using the test method ISO 5658-2 [16] for lateral spread, and the flammability requirement for materials in the engine compartments. The UNECE Regulation No.118 has received criticism [26-28] mainly because the flammability tests are only suitable for small ignition sources such as a lighter. Further studies [29] have compared tests methods for analysing the flammability of interior materials.

In terms of the improvement of other layers of fire protection, the use of alarms in the engine compartment has been required since 2012 [19]. Fire extinguishers and first-aid equipment should be included. Buses shall be equipped with an alarm system detecting either an excess temperature or smoke in the toilet compartments, driver's sleeping compartments and all other separate compartments (added in 2012 [19]).

The driver's compartment shall be provided with an acoustic and visual signal (added in the last update in 2014) operational whenever the engine start device is operated. On top of the requirements on prevention, Regulation 107 includes specification related to exits and emergency characteristics (e.g. number, position and width), driver's compartment and interior lighting.

5. Statistical Data on Fire Incidents in UK Buses

A key aspect to understand fire protection of any system is statistical data. But data on bus fires is rather inadequate worldwide with only a few good national datasets from Sweden [13, 30], Norway [13] and the USA [14]. Smaller dataset exist for UK, Germany and Finland [1, 31-33].

This paper puts together a database of bus fire statistics bringing together UK data from 1964 to 2014 with a gap between 1970 and 1983. Only data from 1994 to 2013 has been analysed in this paper. The available data is focused on the number of bus fires per year (with no distinction between accidental and deliberate fires and between buses, coaches and minibuses). The number of deaths and injuries is only registered between 1964 and 1969 [15], and between 2010 and 2014 [1]. The range of years is too narrow to quantify how much each layer impacts on the number of casualties.

The Department of Communities and Local Government (DCLG) in the UK publishes electronic annual bulletins on fire statistics from 2000 onwards [1]. The statistics in these bulletins are compiled from Fire and Rescue Service records of incidents attended by Fire and Rescue Services in Great Britain (including England, Scotland and Wales). Prior to 2009, the publication was focused in the UK (including England, Scotland, Wales and Northern Ireland). Prior to 2000, The Home Office was responsible for publishing the bulletins with the fire statistics of fires attended by the local authority fire brigade in the UK. Those bulletins detailed statistics on fires, casualties and false alarms in buildings.

In 2008 the Fire and Rescue Services changed the collection method from paper based on the Fire Damage Report (FDR1) to the Incident Reporting System (IRS) [34]. These bulletins are based on sample data; only 2005 statistics used the entire FDR1 dataset for calculations. According to [34], the DCLG converted the primary fires recorded by brigades into analytic variables by using a statistical analysis package. The available information does not allow us to identify if this change could affect the annual data at some point. For this reason, in this paper the data in the annual bulletins are used as the total population of bus fires. The UK bulletins collect fire statistics since 1994; however the number of bus fires was included in these statistics since 1996.

An additional dataset on bus fires in the UK has been observed for the period between 1964 and 1969 [15]. This Fire research note was published in 1972 by the Fire Research Station at BRE. This dataset includes annual data on the number of bus fires in this period as well as additional information such as the number of deaths and injuries, location of the fire in the vehicle and the year of manufacture of vehicle in which fire occurred.

Both, the UK bulletins and the Fire Research note include the number of fire events registered in buses, coaches and minibuses, with no distinction between these three categories.

It is not possible to identify if other specific requirements, such as other UK regulations or insurance companies requirements, were applied to UK buses at some point. For this reason, this paper is only focusing on the mandatory requirements which were European Regulations at the time. As European Regulations only applied to buses carrying more than 22 passengers, it is not possible to know which coaches and minibuses are required to meet these regulations since the UK statistics do not differ between the three categories and does not specify the coach and minibus characteristics. This already suggests a data gap with room for improvements.

In order to obtain the annual frequency of bus fires per vehicle, the size of the bus fleet is required, and we collected this information from the Department for Transport [1]. The annual census includes as buses all coaches, buses and minibuses (minibuses can carry no more than sixteen passengers) used for commercial purposes. It does not specify if school buses are included. Figure 2 shows the data on the annual number of fires and the annual frequency of bus fires per vehicle (number of fire events per 1000 vehicles licenced) in the UK.

As shown in Figure 2, an average of 327 bus fires per year was registered in the UK between 1964 and 1969. This average more than doubled to 761 for the period between 1984 and 2013. The large increase in the number of bus fires is in part due to the increase in the size of the UK bus fleet during this period. A total of 86,000 buses were licenced in 1964, and the fleet had nearly doubled by 2013 to a size of 164,410 buses. Since 1994, the bus fleet increased annually with an average of 11,200 new buses per year. As Figure 2 shows, there was a drop in 1993 on the frequency of bus fires per vehicle. This drop was potentially caused by the collection method. Until 1993, the DVLA (Driver and Vehicle Licensing Agency) was responsible for annual vehicle census while figures from 1993 onwards originate from the Department for Transport. Available information does not allow us to identify if the collection methods before and after 1993 are the similar. As next sections show, the analysis conducted in this paper is focused on the fire statistics since 1994 so that the possible distinction between collection methods does not affect to the results.

Figure 2. Number of bus fires and frequency of bus fires per vehicles from 1964 to 2013 (note that frequency of bus fire per vehicle is expressed as the annual number of bus fires per 1000 vehicles licenced).

6. Statistical Data on Fire Incidents in UK Buses

Our key method for quantifying the layers of fire protection is a cross analysis of the regulations and the annual statistics in bus fires. The changes in the regulations over the years led to the strengthening of layers of fire protection in buses. Note that the fire data does not differentiate between coaches, buses and minibuses (since UK database does not collect this information), though the regulations only apply to buses and coaches (vehicles carrying more than 22 people). Data set compiled by the Department for Transport in the UK on the number of buses licenced per year differs between buses and coaches and minibuses. Although it is not possible to know how many coaches can carry more than 22 passengers, we expect that about 87% of those vehicles are buses and coaches for which the regulations apply.

The bus fleet manufactured after a regulation change contains the corresponding enhancement. The replacement of the bus fleet in the UK is gradual and during some years after a layer is included or boosted, the total bus fleet licenced in the UK contains both, old (pre-regulation buses) and new buses (post-regulation buses). The size of the post-regulation bus fleet will increase annually, as the pre-regulation bus fleet will decrease.

6.1 The evolution of the bus fleet in the UK

The Department for Transport in the UK registers annually, the total number of buses in the UK as well as the number of new buses licensed each year. Based on this information, it is possible to evaluate the evolution of the fleet after a standard modification.

As section 4 shows, for the analysed period and dataset on bus fires, the European Directive 95/28/EC and UNECE regulation No. 107 enhanced the prevention layer twice, in 1995 and 2001 respectively.

The bus fleet manufactured from 1995 to 2001 contains the prevention layer improved by the European Directive 95/28/EC. The bus fleet manufactured since 2001 also includes the improvements provided by the UNECE regulation No. 107. The following nomenclature will be used throughout the rest of the paper.

- y_{95} - Size of the fleet of buses manufactured before the European Directive 95/28/EC in 1995.
- y'_{95} - Size of the fleet of buses manufactured after the European Directive 95/28/EC in 1995 but before UNECE regulation No. 107 in 2001.
- y''_{01} - Size of the fleet of buses manufactured after the UNECE regulation No. 107 in 2001.

Based on the statistical data from the Department for Transport in the UK (total number of buses and new buses licensed per year), the evolution of the size of these three bus fleets since 1995 (y_{95} , y'_{95} and y''_{01}) can be obtained (see Figure 3). Note that buses include buses, coaches and minibuses.

Figure 3. Evolution of buses manufactured before 1995, from 1995 to 2001 and buses manufactured after 2001 during the period of 1995 to 2013.

As shown in Fig.3 and under the reasonable assumption that the bus fleet is progressively replaced, from 1995 to 2000, y_{95} decreases as y'_{95} increases. In addition, there is a period between 2001 and 2010, when the three bus fleets exits (in different proportions) at the same time. After 2010, only y'_{95} and y''_{01} exist.

6.2 The quantification of prevention layer in UK buses

As it has been explained in section 3, key aspects to identify and quantify the layers of fire protection are statistical data and its level of detail and fire protection regulations.

During the period of analysis (1994 and 2013) the changes in the regulations in 1995 (prevention layer) and 2001 (prevention, passive system and evacuation layers) affected the number of bus fires. Passive system and evacuation layers do not affect the number of bus fires, so the available data (annual number of bus fires and buses licenced) allows the authors to identify and quantify how much the prevention layer has reduced the number of fires during the years in UK buses. On the basis of a wider statistical dataset and fire regulations, the proposed method can be extrapolated to other scenarios and layers.

The risk in vehicle fires should be measured by fires per vehicle-mile or casualties per passenger-mile. As discussed above, bus fire statistics in the UK is focused on the total number of bus fires per year. For this reason, this paper proposes the use of frequency of bus fire per vehicle to measure the impact of layers of fire protection instead of probability.

We can quantify the impact of the prevention layer (or any other layer) by comparing the frequency of bus fire per vehicle before and after changing the fire protection regulation which affects that layer.

In buses, the impact of the prevention layer is obtained by assessing the frequency of bus fires per vehicle in the buses manufactured before a regulation change versus the frequency of bus fires per vehicle in buses manufactured after a regulation change. The comparison of these frequencies of bus fires per vehicle will show how much a change in a regulation has impacted to the number of bus fires.

This paper is based on the hypothesis that all the buses of each fleet (y_{95} , y'_{95} and y''_{01}) have the same level of fire protection. For this reason, the frequency of bus fire per vehicle in each bus fleet is similar, and it is assumed that during the years of interest, that probability is constant. In addition, the following nomenclatures will be used throughout the paper:

- F_{95} - Frequency of bus fires per vehicle in a bus from the pre 1995 fleet.
- F'_{95} - Frequency of bus fires per vehicle between 1995 and 2001 fleet.
- F''_{01} - Frequency of bus fires per vehicle in a bus in the 2001 fleet.

Based on the information of how the bus fleet replacement takes place in the UK after the regulation modification in 1995 and in 2001 and the previous hypothesis, Eq. (1) calculates the frequency of bus fires per vehicle in pre-regulation (p) and post-regulation buses (p').

$$f_i = F \cdot y_i + F' \cdot y'_i \quad \text{Eq. (1)}$$

Where, f_i is the number of bus fires in year i , y_i is the number of buses in year i manufactured before the regulation change and y_i'' is the number of buses in year i manufactured after the regulation change.

Considering the three bus fleets during the years of interest and based on equation 1, the following equation 2 is proposed as a functional relationship to obtain the frequency of bus fires per vehicle in each bus fleet (F_{1995} , F_{1995}' and F_{2001}'')

$$f_i = F_{95} \cdot y_{95} + F_{95}' \cdot y_{95}' + F_{01}'' \cdot y_{01}'' \quad \text{Eq. (2)}$$

Based on the annual number of bus fires (f_i) extracted from the UK data and the three bus fleets (y_{95} , y_{95}' and y_{01}''), the frequencies of bus fires per vehicle (F_{95} , F_{95}' and F_{01}'') are calculated by optimizing the frequencies of bus fires to fit Eq. (2).

The mathematical optimization seeks to minimize the difference between the numbers of bus fires each year between 1995 and 2001 registered in the annual bulletins of fire statistics and the optimized frequency of bus fire f_i (an iterative "goal seek" approach).

The best-optimized frequencies of bus fire per vehicle are:

Table 2. Frequency of bus fires per vehicle before 1995, between 1995 and 2001 and after 2001 obtained by an iterative "goal seek" approach of Eq.2.

Frequency of bus fires per vehicle	Optimized parameters
F_{1995}	4.850±0.003
F_{1995}'	4.210±0.003
F_{2001}''	2.990±0.003

The error obtained is the average relative error in the optimization of these three variables.

The impact of each regulation modification is evaluated by dividing the frequencies of bus fire per vehicle before and

after a change. Based on the optimized values for F_{95} , F_{95}' , F_{01}'' and equation 2, Figure 4 shows the best-fit bus fires.

Figure 4. Annual number of bus fires obtained from the UK statistics (this is a zoom of Fig.2) versus the number of bus fires predicted by Eq. (2).

In order to smooth out short-term fluctuations in the number of bus fires (UK data), the moving average was obtained. As Fig.4 shows, Eq.2 (using the best-optimized frequencies of bus fires per vehicle) predicts the number of bus fires in the UK with a high accuracy.

The variability between the number of bus fires (and its moving average) and the best-fit bus fires in Fig.3 is mainly caused by the assumption of the constant probabilities. It should be noted that the updates in the regulations might slightly affect these frequencies of bus fires per vehicle during a period.

Based on the best-fit frequencies of bus fires per vehicle, we can compare the frequency of bus fires per vehicle immediately after and before the regulation changes so that we can quantify the impact of the prevention layer.

The comparison of F_{95} and F_{95}' allows us to quantify how much the enhancement of the prevention layer in 1995 reduces the frequency of bus fires per vehicles.

$$r_{95} = \frac{F_{95}}{F_{95}'} = 1.152 \pm 0.002 \quad \text{Eq. (3)}$$

$$r_{01} = \frac{F'_{95}}{F''_{01}} = 1.408 \pm 0.002 \quad \text{Eq. (4)}$$

As expected, the enhancement of the prevention layer led to a decrease in the number of bus fires. Eq. (3) shows that the 95/28/EC in 1995, which is based on flammability tests for the passenger compartment, reduced the number of bus fires by up to 11%. On the top of that, the UNECE Regulation No.117 reduced the number of bus fires by up to 29%. To quantify the overall impact of prevention layer (R) reducing the frequency of fires in UK buses, Eq. (3) is extrapolated to F_{95} and F''_{01} so that:

$$R = 1.622 \pm 0.002 \quad \text{Eq. (5)}$$

Note that the errors in overall Ratio R, ratio for 1995 r_{95} and ratio for 2001 r_{01} are estimated as indirect measurement in Eq. (4) considering the relative errors of the different terms.

The analysis of layers of fire protection in buses shows that the prevention is a key aspect as the regulations has been focused on improving this layer. The enhancement of the prevention layer over the years has reduced by up to 38% the overall number of bus fires. Even when the probability of bus fires is higher than other modes of transport, fire safety remains substantially lower and the applicability of some regulations such as the flammability tests is still under discussion.

7 Conclusions

In this paper, we present a novel approach to quantify the impact of prevention layer in UK buses from 1964 to 2013.

The fire safety of passenger transport in buses has received very little attention in the technical literature. However, fire statistics show that buses are much riskier than other modes of transport like cars, shipping, rolling stock or aviation. This is in great part due to the lower fire safety a regulatory requirement for buses, which are less stringent than the other modes of transport.

The 95/28/EC (updated by the UNECE Regulation N.118), and the UN ECE Regulation N.107 in 2001 and its updates, have enhanced the fire prevention in buses.

This novel approach uses bus fire statistics collected between 1994 and 2013. It is not possible to know if other specific requirements have also improved the fire safety in the entire or part of the bus fleet in UK during this time. However, the mandatory character of European Regulations ensures that new licenced buses after a change in these regulations shall include the required improvements.

The proposed methodology allow us to quantify the impact of fire prevention in buses by using an overall database, even when not all the factors are clearly identify. The cross-analysis of the frequency of bus fires and the gradual replacement of UK buses shows that the prevention layer has reduced up to 37% the number of bus fires in the UK.

This is the first time that the impact of fire prevention is quantified in buses, making a case for their high effectiveness. Considering that the frequency of bus fires per vehicle is higher than other modes of transport, identifying the strengths and weaknesses in the layers of fire protection in buses is a key aspect for further development of current regulations.

The approach developed here is novel and can be used to analyze other data sets and modes of transport. In addition, based on the available data the methodology can be applied to other layers of fire protection. It should be noted that the more detailed statistics, the more accurate results. The enhancement in data collection methods for fire statistics (automatic data collection, big data techniques, etc.) will be able to register more information in fires such as the specific fire cause. In this case, we expect that the proposed methodology will allow us to identify other layers of fire protection with a higher level of detailed.

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